

TABLE 1—INFRARED ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) OF Zn(II), Cd(II) AND Hg(II) COMPLEXES OF N,N,N',N'-TETRAMETHYLTHIURAMDISULPHIDE

Compound	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$	Other vibrations
Zn(Me ₄ tds)Cl ₂	1540 (s,br)	1250 (s)	960 (s)	879 (w)	240 ($\nu\text{Zn}-\text{Cl}$)
Zn(Me ₄ tds)Br ₂	1480 (m)	1235 (s)	980 (m)	850 (m)	
Zn(Me ₄ tds)I ₂	1500 (s)	1240 (s)	970 (s)	—	
Zn(Me ₄ tds)(NOS) ₂	1500 (s)	1235 (m)	970 (s)	860 (w)	2040, 2075(νCN), 800(νCS)
Cd(Me ₄ tds)Cl ₂	1510 (s)	1240 (s)	958 (s)	800 (w)	450 (δNCS)
Cd(Me ₄ tds)Br ₂	1500 (s,br)	1240 (s)	970 (s)	850 (s)	—
Cd(Me ₄ tds)I ₂	1500 (s,br)	1240 (m)	975 (s)	850 (s)	
Cd(Me ₄ tds)(NOS) ₂	1510 (m)	1235 (s)	970 (s)	845 (s)	2060(νCN), 830(νCS), 490(δNCS)
Cd(Me ₄ tds)(CH ₃ COO) ₂	1500 (m)	1240 (s)	950 (s)	850 (w)	
Hg(Me ₄ tds)Cl ₂	1530 (m,br)	1230 (s)	960 (s)	850 (w)	255($\nu\delta\text{Hg}-\text{Cl}$)
Hg(Me ₄ tds)Br ₂	1505 (m)	1250 (s)	965 (s)	855 (w)	
Hg(Me ₄ tds)I ₂	1510 (s,br)	1240 (s)	960 (s)	850 (w)	
Hg(Me ₄ tds)(SCN) ₂	1490 (m,br)	1242 (m)	960 (s)	875 (w)	2125(νCN), 720(νCS), 450(δSCN), 270($\nu\text{Hg}-\text{SCN}$)
Hg(Me ₄ tds)(NO ₃) ₂	1540 (m,br)	1250 (s)	955 (s)	840 (w)	

mercury(II) nitrate complex show a monodentate bonding mode of nitrate in the complex¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

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Complexes of Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) with *p*-Hydroxyphenylthiohydrazide

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COMPLEXES of some transition metals with thiohydrazide derivatives have been reported from this laboratory¹⁻³ and other workers⁴⁻⁷. In present paper we are reporting the complexes of Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) with *p*-hydroxyphenylthiohydrazide (phphH).

p-Hydroxyphenylthiohydrazide is a potent nitrogen, sulphur and oxygen donor ligand and can coordinate as neutral, monoanionic and dianionic ligand in thione-thiol tautomers A and B. However, in neutral or acidic medium it coordinates as simple thiohydrazide¹⁻⁷.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by reported method⁸. The metal salts and chemicals used were of B. D. H., AnalaR grade reagent.

Preparation of complexes :

[Ni(phphH)₂]₂X₂, (X = Cl, NO₃ or $\frac{1}{2}$ SO₄): Methanolic solution of hydrated nickel(II) salt (0.01 mol in 50 ml) was treated with 5% solution of the ligand dissolved in hot methanol. The pH of the resulting solution was adjusted to 2-3 by adding a few drops of appropriate acid when orange-yellow to orange-red complex salt separated slowly. The product was filtered, washed with a little methanol and dried in a desiccator over CaCl₂.

TABLE 1

Complex (LH = phpthH)	Colour	μ_{eff} (304-305K) B.M.	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			Reflectance band position cm ⁻¹
			Metal	Nitrogen	Cl/SO ₄	
[Ni(LH) ₂]Cl ₂	Orange yellow	Dia.	12.41 (12.60)	11.90 (12.02)	15.35 (15.24)	22220 w 19280 sh
[Ni(LH) ₂]SO ₄	Orange red	Dia.	11.89 (11.96)	11.26 (11.41)	19.05 (19.56)	21980 m 20410 m
[Ni(LH) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	Orange red	Dia.	11.25 (11.32)	15.96 (16.20)	—	—
[NiL ₂]	Cream yellow	Dia.	14.67 (14.89)	13.90 (14.19)	—	26670, 21280 m
[CuL ₂]	Dark brown	1.65	15.72 (15.98)	13.90 (14.09)	—	26300 m 14700-12200 br
[Cu(LH)Cl ₂]	Deep green	1.86	21.44 (20.99)	9.18 (9.25)	23.66 (23.47)	25000 br 16130-12200 wbr
[Cu(LH)Br ₂]	Brown	1.11	16.51 (16.23)	6.92 (7.15)	40.05 (40.84)	25000 br 15150-12820 br
[ZnL ₂]	Cream yellow	Dia.	16.65 (16.38)	14.26 (14.05)	—	—
[CdL ₂]	Yellow	Dia.	23.49 (23.69)	11.62 (11.79)	—	—
[HgL ₂]	Cream colour	Dia.	37.01 (37.53)	10.21 (10.47)	—	—
[Hg(LH)Cl ₂]	Cream colour	Dia.	45.98 (45.62)	6.12 (6.36)	15.86 (16.15)	—

[M(phpth)₂], (M = Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺ or Hg²⁺): An aqueous methanolic solution of hydrated metal acetate (0.01 mol in 50 ml) was added to a methanolic solution of the ligand in 1 : 2 molar ratio with stirring. From the resulting solution the bis-chelated inner complex separated out slowly either on refluxing or diluting the refluxate with excess of water. The product was filtered, washed with aqueous methanol and dried *in vacuo* over CaCl₂.

[M(phpthH)Cl₂], (M = Cu²⁺ or Hg²⁺) and [Cu(phpthH)Br₂]: About 1.5 g of metal halide was dissolved in 40 ml of cold methanol and treated with cold methanolic solution of the ligand in 1 : 1 molar ratio. From the resulting solution fine crystalline product separated out gradually on stirring. The product was filtered immediately, washed with cold methanol and dried as above.

The result of elemental analysis, colour, magnetic moment values at 304-305K and solid reflectance band positions of the complexes are given in Table 1. Magnetic susceptibility and electronic spectra of the complexes were measured as reported earlier¹⁻³.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis (Table 1) indicates that in neutral medium, phpthH acts as a monoanionic ligand and forms neutral bis-chelates [M(phpth)₂] with Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cu²⁺, Cd²⁺ or Hg²⁺, but in acidic medium it coordinates as neutral chelating molecule forming complex salts [Ni(phpthH)₂]X₂ (X = Cl, NO₃ or $\frac{1}{2}$ SO₄) and dihalo complexes [M(phpthH)Cl₂] (M = Hg²⁺ or Cu²⁺) and [Cu(phpthH)Br₂]. Excepting Cu(II), the complexes of Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) are diamagnetic. Diamagnetism of Ni(II) indicates four coordinated square planar

structure of Ni(II) complexes. Magnetic moment value of [Cu(phpthH)Cl₂], calculated on making correction for T.I.P. contribution, was found to be 1.86 B.M., which is similar to magnetically dilute copper(II) complexes⁹. The inner chelates [Cu(phpth)₂] and [Cu(phpthH)Br₂] show subnormal magnetic moment value (Table 1).

The diffused reflectance spectra of Ni(II) complexes display two medium bands or shoulders between 22220-26680 and 19230-21280 cm⁻¹, assignable to ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{3g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g} transitions in square planar field¹⁰. The solid reflectance spectra of [Cu(phpthH)X₂], (X = Cl or Br) and [Cu(phpth)₂] display a strong absorption between 25000 and 26300 cm⁻¹, probably charge transfer type, and another medium or weak broad asymmetric band at 16130-12220 cm⁻¹ assignable to E_g → T_{2g} or combination of ²B_{1g} → ²E_g and ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g} transitions in distorted octahedral field¹¹. From the stoichiometry, Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes [M(phpth)₂] (M = Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺ or Hg²⁺) and [Hg(phpthH)Cl₂] are tentatively suggested to possess tetrahedral geometry, since tetrahedral geometry is more preferred structure for these metal complexes¹².

IR spectra: The ir spectra of ligand and its complexes display very broad and medium band between 3250 and 3030 cm⁻¹ due to NH₂ and NH stretching frequencies¹³. In free ligand, a medium and broad band, observed at 2090-2040 cm⁻¹, is attributed to intermolecular hydrogen bonded OH frequency¹⁴. The band is retained in almost all its complexes indicating that phenolic OH is not involved in coordination. The ligand displays a number of ir bands at 1575 (s, br), 1548 (sh), 1480 (m, br), 1440 (m, br), 1390 (w), 1280 (m), 1257 (m), 1225 (s, br), 1170 (m), 1145 (m, br), 1012 (s), 1000 (sh), 945 (s), 830 (s), 815 (m), 730 (m, br), 675 (m,

br), 650 (m, br), 605 (w), 580 (m) and 520 (s) cm^{-1} arising from different modes of phenyl ring, thiohydrazide group and phenolic OH group vibrations. A broad and strong band at 1575 cm^{-1} can be attributed to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C}) + \delta\text{NH}_2$ vibration of thiohydrazide group^{15,16} which shifts to higher frequencies by 5-10 cm^{-1} . The symmetric (NH_2) deformation vibration of phpthH (at 1225 cm^{-1}) shifts to higher frequencies by 15-35 cm^{-1} in complexes, indicating the co-ordination of hydrazine part terminal nitrogen with metal atom^{15,16}.

Thioamide bands I, II and III located at 1548, 1280 and 1012 cm^{-1} are also shifted to higher frequencies by 10-90 cm^{-1} while thioamide band IV (730 cm^{-1}) shifts to lower frequencies by 10-50 cm^{-1} in its complexes on coordination^{16,17}. Thus, from the study of the ir spectra of the ligand and its complexes, it is inferred that thioamide sulphur and thiohydrazide part terminal nitrogen are involved in coordination¹⁷. In far infrared region, the complexes display two to three new bands between 450 and 320 cm^{-1} region. The ir band located at 450-400 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ and between 350 and 320 cm^{-1} to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$ vibrations^{18,19}.

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Dehydration-Rehydration Behaviour of Zirconium and Thorium Hydroxide Hydrogel in Relation to Temperature of Heat Treatment

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THE hydroxide hydrogels of zirconium and thorium can be prepared in various ways¹⁻⁴ and the resultant products also differ in their physico-chemical characteristics. These gel materials are very important for studying many high temperature reactions. Hydrous zirconia shows signs of crystallinity⁵ with increase in drying temperature as evidenced by X-ray analysis. Precipitated amorphous zirconia inverts to tetragonal ZrO_2 at 400° and monoclinic at 600-800°. With this inversion all identity as hydrous zirconia disappears but traces of water persists upto about 1000°.

Maiti *et al*⁶ observed that the transition temperature of phase changes increases with increase in crystallite size. Considering the importance of hydroxide gels of tetravalent cations such as Zr^{4+} and Th^{4+} the study of the flexibility of dehydration-rehydration was undertaken. In this part heat treatment was carried out under equilibrium condition upto 900°.

Experimental

Hydrogels of zirconium and thorium were prepared from acidic solutions of zirconium nitrate and thorium nitrate by interaction with $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl-NH}_4\text{OH}$ buffer at pH 9. After proper ageing they were processed in accordance with literature method¹⁰ to get rid of the extraneous impurities.

Equilibrium dehydration-rehydration was studied by following the procedure as adopted by Mitra *et al*¹¹.

Results and Discussion

The hydroxide gels of zirconium and thorium, as synthesised under present experimental conditions, were amorphous in nature as evidenced by X-ray analysis (Fig. not shown). The equilibrium dehydration curves were discontinuous in nature (Fig. 1). Both these hydrogels showed inflection, in the early stage due to removal of loosely bound water and at higher temperature due to expulsion of constitutional hydroxyl groups. The temperatures of inflection were comparatively high with thorium hydroxide gel. In case of thorium hydroxide gel the dehydration loss above 500° was not very significant (Fig. 1) whereas in case of zirconium hydroxide gel the hydroxyl groups are bonded with higher